

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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Project title: Advancing Functional Renormalization for Frustrated Quantum Spins

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2 Summary

2.1 Kurzfassung

Wir berichten über bedeutende methodische Fortschritte in der theoretischen Beschreibung frustrierter und hochdimensionaler Quantenspinsysteme im thermischen Gleichgewicht. Der ursprüngliche Schwerpunkt des Projekts (funktionale Renormierungsgruppe) wurde zugunsten von Reihenentwicklungen zu hohen Ordnungen geändert. Diese ermöglichten es, präzise Korrekturen über die Mean-Field Approximation hinaus zu berechnen, z.B. für hochdimensionale oder langreichweitig wechselwirkende Modelle. Eine weitere Variante erlaubte eine Hochtemperatur-Reihenentwicklung der Frequenzmomente der dynamische Strukturfaktoren. Die Rekonstruktion dieser Strukturfaktoren aus ihren Momenten eröffnet einen neuen Zugang zu dieser wichtigen und auch experimentell messbaren Größe.

2.2 Summary

We report on substantial methodological progress in the theoretical description of frustrated and high-dimensional quantum spin system in thermal equilibrium. The initial scope of the proposal on functional renormalization type approaches was changed in favor for high-order perturbative expansions. These allowed to accurately compute beyond mean-field corrections for high-dimensional or long-range interacting models. Another incarnation allowed for a high-temperature series expansion of frequency moments for dynamic structure factors. Reconstruction of the latter yields access to this important and also experimentally measurable quantity.

3 Progress Report

3.1 Background and objectives of the project

The original project proposal in late 2022 considered a novel theoretical scheme for the analysis of frustrated and high-dimensional quantum spin models in thermal equilibrium. Such models are relevant both in solid-state Mott insulators or in cold-atom based artificial quantum simulation platforms. Prior to the proposal we had worked on various theoretical approaches to such models that had in common that spin operators S_i^α (with $\alpha = x, y, z$) were represented by a bilinear of auxiliary fermionic degrees of freedom. When spin models like the paradigmatic Heisenberg model

$$H = \sum_{i < i'} J_{ii'} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_{i'} \quad (1)$$

are rewritten using such “pseudo-fermions”, established theoretical methods in the Matsubara many-body formalism can be applied. We had so far focused on the functional renormalization group (fRG) [1, 2]. The project proposal was motivated by the recent advances from the Kopietz group at Frankfurt University where a different variant of the fRG, called spin-fRG, was introduced [3–5].

In a nutshell, the idea of spin-fRG was to avoid the unphysical fermionic degrees of freedom and work directly with correlation functions of spin operators. Curiously, in this case the fRG can be still applied with some modifications but the absence of Wick’s theorem for spin operators renders the truncation of the flow-equation hierarchy far from trivial. While Kopietz and coworkers used heavy approximations motivated on a case by case basis to keep their calculations tractable, our idea was to achieve a more generally applicable but numerically involved solution of the flow equations for spin-fRG. With our expertise in writing high performance fRG codes in the pseudo-fermionic case we hoped to harness the full methodological power of the spin-fRG that would give direct access to four spin expectation values encoding spin stiffness, support magnetic fields or time-reversal symmetry breaking. We also planned to use these observables to detect valence-bond solids and chiral spin-liquids.

First, we fully derived the exact general spin-fRG flow equations for spin vertices up to the 4-particle level. We performed benchmarks on small spin-clusters, where exact results for all vertices are readily available from exact diagonalization and the spectral representation of multi-point Matsubara correlation function which we derived earlier [6]. However, in comparison to very simple truncation strategies with only a flowing 2-point vertex, no improvements of the resulting correlation functions could be observed despite considerable effort. In particular, we included the full flowing 3- and 4-point vertices, and kept the numerically intractable 5- and 6-point vertices at their non-zero initial values. We have spend almost a year in trying to understand and solve this problem by using more sophisticated approximations for the 5- and 6-point vertices to adapt them during the flow. However, this did not lead to any breakthroughs. Seen from a high level, the ultimate reason for this failure likely lies in the complexity of the algebra of spin operators in comparison to the fermionic case. Only the latter fulfill a Wick theorem that ensures the vanishing of higher-than 4-point vertices at the start of the flow. For spins, in contrast, vertices at higher order are not only always finite but are seemingly also much stronger interwoven with their lower-order counterparts by the additional operator constraints like, e.g., $\mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_i = S(S + 1)$. Apparently, despite considerable effort, so far we were not able to distill a sufficiently versatile ansatz for higher-order vertices from these relations.

3.2 Description of the project-specific results and findings

The fRG approach is a modern and quite involved way to treat the quantum many-body problem. During the early stages of our project we realized, however, that for spin operators, very little was known about even much simpler approaches to the Matsubara correlators like perturbation theory. Maybe a better understanding and development of plain perturbation theory, say in the form of a high-temperature expansion, would inform more appropriate truncation schemes for spin-fRG?

Our subsequent focus on high-order and/or resummed perturbation expansions for spin systems turned out to be very fruitful in itself. It resulted in four (sub-)projects and associated publications (A)-(D) which are listed in Sec. 4. The implications of these results for the spin-fRG is yet to be explored in the future.

To start, we review two conceptually different but related ways of performing diagrammatic perturbation theory for the Matsubara spin-spin correlator,

$$G_{ii'}^{zz}(i\nu_m) = T \int_0^\beta d\tau d\tau' e^{i\nu_m(\tau-\tau')} \langle \mathcal{T} S_i^z(\tau) S_{i'}^z(\tau') \rangle. \quad (2)$$

For simplicity, we assume the Heisenberg model (1) and consider treating the interacting part $\sim J$ perturbatively, which leaves $H_0 = 0$ as the non-perturbed Hamiltonian. The spin-diagrammatic approach is motivated by the formal expansion of Eq. (2) shown graphically in Fig. 1(b). The following two variants differ in how the required ‘‘V-connected’’ averages are taken. The latter reflect the need to also expand the partition function which appears in the denominator of correlation functions. The first approach by Vaks, Larkin and Pikin [7, 8] requires to resolve this V-connected average by grouping spin operators (black dots) in Fig. 1(b) in brown ellipses that stand for connected time-ordered single-spin correlation functions (cumulants), see Fig. 1(c). Crucially, a given site of the real-space lattice can be associated to one *or more* brown ellipses (‘‘free graphs’’). This flexibility allows directly for resummation schemes that build infinite ‘‘strings’’ of diagrams. The most common example is the identification of the 1-J-irreducible diagrams which can be separated by cutting a single interaction line. The infinite set of such diagrams is denoted by Σ . The Larkin equation resums the infinite series in Fig. 1(d), $G(i\nu_m, \mathbf{k}) = [1 + \Sigma(i\nu_m, \mathbf{k})J(\mathbf{k})]^{-1} \cdot \Sigma(i\nu_m, \mathbf{k})$. Clearly, approximations to $\Sigma(i\nu_m, \mathbf{k})$ are required for practical use.

Another possibility to resolve the averages in Fig. 1(b) is often used in the high-temperature series expansion (HTE) [10]. Here, a similar assignment of (full) single-spin correlators on graph-vertices to lattice sites is required, however each vertex can only be assigned to one lattice site. Resummation is not possible on the diagrammatic level but can be performed on the resulting perturbation series using, e.g., Padé approximants. Note that expansion of the partition function has to be taken care of via sub-graph subtractions.

Crucially, while these diagrammatic expansions were well known in principle, the evaluation of diagrams of even modest orders was not possible until we entered the field. The reason is the very complex nature of the aforementioned high-order free-spin correlation function that appear in the diagram-internal imaginary-time integrals (or Matsubara-frequency sums). Our recently developed ‘‘Kernel-trick’’ [6] however allows to perform these nested time integrals exactly. Its applicability hinges on the simple and local form of $H_0 = 0$ but still works if local magnetic fields are present, see (A).

In article (A) we tabulated the resulting expressions for the diagrams of the 1-J-irreducible parts $\Sigma_{ii'}^{(n)}(i\nu_m)$ for general S , up to order $n \leq n_{max} = 4$ in J and up to the sum over internal lattice sites.

Figure 1: (a) Sketch of typical temperature-field phase diagram of quantum magnets. (b) Diagrammatic representation of the expansion for the Matsubara spin-spin correlator G in the exchange interaction $-J$ (lines), the orders $n = 0, 1, 2$ are shown explicitly. (c) Diagrammatic representation of the V -connected correlators in (b) in terms of imaginary-time ordered connected free-spin correlators (brown ellipses). The 1-J-irreducible diagrams of order J^0 and J^2 are marked with boxes, the infinite sum of all these diagrams constitutes Σ , the 1-J-irreducible part of G . (d) The Larkin equation recombines Σ and J to form G . [Figure reproduced from Ref. (B)].

Figure 2: Ordering temperature for the $S = 1/2$ square lattice Heisenberg FM with couplings decaying as a power law with exponent α . Dots denote reference data from QMC taken from Ref. [9]. Colored lines indicate T_c in MF approximation (green), and adding corrections up to order $[\alpha - 2]^2$ (purple) and $[\alpha - 2]^3$ (magenta), respectively. [Figure reproduced from (B)]

It is well known that using only the order $n = 0$ result in the Larkin equation is equivalent to the mean-field approximation, including higher orders corresponds to corrections. We considered the example of a square-lattice $S = 1/2$ ferromagnet with long range interaction $J_{ij} = J_1/|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j|^\alpha$ with variable exponent α . It is known that the mean-field result for the magnetic ordering temperature T_c (defined via a diverging static correlator) is exact for $\alpha = d = 2$ and we considered $\alpha - 2$ as a small parameter. In Fig. 2 we show the resulting $T_c(\alpha)$ and observe rapid convergence of its expansion in orders of $\alpha - 2$ towards the error controlled quantum Monte Carlo result. We could also treat the gap of the $d = 3$ transverse-field Ising model and the Dicke-Ising model of ground-state superradiance. In the latter case we showed diagrammatically that corrections to the mean-field phase boundary vanish exactly.

In article (B) we applied the formalism from (A) to shed new light at the so called quantum-to-classical correspondence (QCC) found empirically more than a decade ago [11] for Heisenberg models. The QCC claims a match between the real-space static susceptibility pattern of a quantum spin-1/2 model and its classical $S = \infty$ counterpart if the latter is computed at a certain fine-tuned temperature. This puzzling relation was observed via bold-line diagrammatic Monte Carlo (BDMC) simulations in dimensions two and three. The matching was within error bars and seemed valid down to the lowest accessible temperatures T about an order of magnitude smaller than the exchange coupling J . By taking the limit $S \rightarrow \infty$ in our perturbation theory results we recovered the classical limit and could compare this to the quantum case $S = 1/2$. For a Heisenberg model given by the Hamiltonian $H =$

$\frac{J}{\sqrt{V_{\text{BZ}}}} \int d\mathbf{k} \gamma(\mathbf{k}) \mathbf{S}_k \cdot \mathbf{S}_{-k}$ the inverse static ($i\nu_m = 0$) susceptibility can be parameterized by

$$\beta [\chi(\mathbf{k})]^{-1} = f + g\gamma(\mathbf{k}) + \varepsilon(\mathbf{k}), \quad (3)$$

where f and g are dimensionless parameters independent of \mathbf{k} . In mean-field approximation, $f = \frac{3}{S(S+1)}$ and $g = \beta J$. Therefore, $\varepsilon(\mathbf{k})$ describes the deviations of the susceptibility from a (generalized) mean-field form with renormalized parameters f and g that is given by the first two terms of Eq. (3). We dub the approximation of $\varepsilon(\mathbf{k}) = 0$ the *renormalized mean field* (rMF) form. In the temperature region where the rMF is valid, both the classical and the quantum susceptibility have the same functional form that only depends on two parameters. Therefore, it is straightforward to map the normalized susceptibilities onto each other by changing the temperature. We could proof analytically that the first term violating the rMF form at $S = \frac{1}{2}$ is of order $(\beta J)^4$ while the first term that could contribute to $\varepsilon(\mathbf{k})$ in the classical case is of order $(\beta J)^6$. This, however, only proofs the QCC for high temperatures. Remarkably, we could show empirically that the diagrammatic Monte Carlo data for the susceptibility can be very well fitted by the rMF form across for all available temperatures (see Fig. 3(a) for an example of the triangular lattice) with exponential accuracy (shown by the log-plot). We could also fit the rMF form to susceptibility data for the five parameter model on the intertwinced trillium lattice describing the material $\text{K}_2\text{Ni}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$. Fig 3(b) shows the excellent match between the classical Monte Carlo data, the quantum data from pseudofermion-fRG and the rMF. In conclusion, the QCC is directly caused by both the quantum and classical susceptibility being approximately of rMF form for large temperature regions and range of models, but it is not an exact correspondence.

Figure 3: (a) Absolute values of normalized real-space spin susceptibility for AFM $S = 1/2$ Heisenberg models with $J_1 = 1$ and temperature T (dots, data taken from BDMC calculations of Refs. [11–13]) compared to the renormalized MF form (Eq. (3) with $\varepsilon = 0$, circles) parameterized with temperature $T_{MF} = \frac{fS(S+1)}{3g} J$ optimized for best agreement. The almost perfect match for rather low T shows the accuracy of the renormalized MF form. (b) Static spin structure factor of a model for $\text{K}_2\text{Ni}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ along the $(h, l, 0)$ reciprocal space. It shows classical MC results at $T = 0.35J_4$ (top left part), PFFRG results at flow parameter $\Lambda = 0.58J_4$ (top right), and a fit to the renormalized MF form (rMF, lower half) at $T_{MF} = 0.787J_4$. [Figure reproduced from (B)]

Figure 4: Static susceptibility $\chi_{\mathbf{k}}(T)$ versus for the Heisenberg $S = 1/2$ AFM on the triangular lattice at the K -point in the corner of the hexagonal BZ. Results from Dyn-HTE (lines) are compared against the BDMC data obtained by Kulagin et al. in Ref. [11] (dots). The convergence of various Padé approximants denoted by blue linestyles is decent and still improves by using the u -series (for $f = 0.25$, purple lines, same Padé approximants as for x -series). Inset: Example of a graph (lattice snippet) embedded in the triangular lattice. [Figure reproduced from (C).]

To go beyond close to mean-field situations, in project (C) we considered the bare perturbation

theory using the restricted graph approach. Here the spin correlator between two lattice sites can be written as a sum of similar correlators defined on suitable lattice-snippets (graphs) weighted with an embedding factor [10]. Therefore, after the evaluation of the correlator on all possible lattice-snippets with up to n_{\max} edges, these results can be reused. One can then quickly calculate n_{\max} th order perturbation theory results on any lattice. In project (C) we used our Kernel trick to carry out this program for the frequency dependent Matsubara spin correlator. This goes beyond the conventional HTE approach, which so far only considered equal-time correlators. We dubbed the method dynamic-HTE (Dyn-HTE). The results are a simultaneous expansion in $x = J/T$ and inverse Matsubara frequency of the spin-spin correlator $G_{ii'}(i\nu_m)$,

$$T G_{ii'}(i\nu_m) = \begin{cases} p_{ii'}^{(0)}(x), & m = 0, \\ \sum_{r=1}^{r_{\max}} p_{ii'}^{(2r)}(x) \left(\frac{x}{2\pi m}\right)^{2r} + \mathcal{O}(x^{n_{\max}+1}), & m \neq 0, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $p^{(2r)}(x)$ are polynomials of degree $n_{\max} - 2r$. We have exactly calculated their coefficients of the spin correlation functions on all possible $\sim 1.6 \times 10^6$ lattice-snippets which appear up to order $n_{\max} = 12$, for $S \in \{\frac{1}{2}, 1\}$. Our results are distributed together with a code to calculate the embedding factors for arbitrary lattices in our open source software (E). A sketch of a third order graph and its embedding into the triangular lattice can be seen in the inset of Fig. 4. We thoroughly benchmarked our code against exact results on finite spin clusters, quantum Monte Carlo results on 1D systems and equal-time correlators from HTE expansions.

As an application, we computed the static susceptibility on the triangular lattice where we found clear deviations from earlier diagrammatic Monte Carlo studies, see Fig. 4. The good convergence of various Padé approximants of our perturbative series support the validity of our data. Remarkably, we could verify that also the static susceptibility of up to 12th order for lattices including the triangular, kagome and pyrochlore are consistent with the renormalized mean field form discovered in project (B) to very high accuracy.

While the Dyn-HTE allows us to calculate the Matsubara correlator down to reasonably low T/J , the resulting data at finite Matsubara frequency $i\nu_m \neq 0$ does not directly relate to any physical observable. In contrast, the *real* frequency dynamic structure factor (DSF) $S(\mathbf{k}, \omega)$ is among the most feature-packed experimental observables for quantum spin systems in equilibrium. It is defined as a spatial and temporal Fourier transform of the real-time spin-spin correlator, $\langle S_i^z(t) S_{i'}^z \rangle$. For solid state samples, the DSF is directly accessible via inelastic neutron scattering (INS) in a momentum-resolved manner. However, from a theory perspective the DSF is often hard to simulate in an unbiased and accurate way, especially for frustrated and high-dimensional models at intermediate temperature.

In article (D) we identified a direct correspondence between the polynomials $p_{\mathbf{k}}^{(2r)}(x)$ in the Matsubara correlator's Dyn-HTE (4) and the frequency moments of the spectral function $A_{\mathbf{k}}(\omega)$. The latter is linked to the DSF by the fluctuation dissipation relation $S(\mathbf{k}, \omega) = [2\pi(1 - e^{-\beta\omega})]^{-1} A_{\mathbf{k}}(\omega)$. From the moments, we were able to reconstruct $A_{\mathbf{k}}(\omega)$ via its continued fraction representation with positive definite parameters. Since we only know the HTE of a finite number of moments to a finite expansion order, we resummed the first $r_{\max} \simeq 4$ moments using various Padé approximants to recover the first r_{\max} continued fraction parameters. We then followed Ref. [14] and extrapolated them linearly to recover a *faithful* continuous, non-negative and properly symmetric spectral function. Despite the modest number of moments, these results go considerably beyond the previously used Gaussian approximation with

Figure 5: DSF for the Heisenberg $S = 1/2$ AFM chain at $x = J/T = 4$. Top: Dyn-HTE results based on extrapolation of moments $r \leq 3$. Middle: DMRG data reproduced from Ref. [15]. Bottom: Linecuts for $S(\mathbf{k}, \omega)$ at $\mathbf{k} \in \{0.2\pi, \pi\}$. The lattice spacing is set to unity. [Figure reproduced from (D)].

Figure 6: (a) DSF from Dyn-HTE for the $S = 1$ Heisenberg AFM on the pyrochlore lattice at $\mathbf{k} = (2, 2, l)$ and where $J = 2.4 \text{ meV}$. The resummation is done via u-Padé with $f = 0.6$. (b) Experimental INS data for $\text{NaCaNi}_2\text{F}_7$ at $x \simeq 15$, from Ref. [16]. [Figure reproduced from (D).]

$r_{\text{max}} \simeq 1$.

We benchmarked the so obtained DSF for the 1D chain against DMRG, finding very good agreement down to temperatures $J/4$, see Fig. 5. For the spin-1 chain, the spectrum reproduced the expected DMRG (para)-magnon dispersion, including temperature-softened signatures of the Haldane gap, see (D). In addition, at $T = J/4$ the method correctly captured the (para)-magnon dispersion of the 2D square-lattice antiferromagnet as known from QMC. These results establish the validity of our method.

Now that we were confident in the accuracy of the method and having computed all possible lattice-snippets (graphs) up to 12th order, we were able to generate DSFs for one-parameter Heisenberg models on *any* lattice. We chose to focus on the spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ triangular lattice antiferromagnet and the spin-1 antiferromagnet on the pyrochlore lattice.

The triangular lattice model exhibits 120° -order at $T = 0$. For $\frac{1}{4} \lesssim T/J \lesssim 1$, however, an enigmatic anomaly occurs: As first found by conventional HTE, static properties deviate strongly from renormalized-classical predictions [17, 18]. We were able to show a temperature-frequency scaling of the DSF at the ordering wavevector. This hints that the anomalous temperature regime might be explained by a quantum critical fan, possibly emerging from the quantum critical point of the J_1 - J_2 -model that is very close in parameter space ($J_2 \gtrsim 0.06J_1$).

The spin-1 pyrochlore material $\text{NaCaNi}_2\text{F}_7$ is known to be approximately described by a Heisenberg model with possibly smaller corrections like biquadratic interactions. Multiple semiclassical methods have been employed to compute the DSF of the Heisenberg model on this lattice [19, 20], but a faithful quantum calculation has not been achieved. With the Dyn-HTE, we closed this gap. A comparison between Dyn-HTE results and INS data can be seen in Fig. 6. There are minor quantitative differences that can be explained by Dyn-HTEs temperature being about three times larger than in the experiment and

the aforementioned beyond-Heisenberg corrections in the true model. However most features match well, like the “V” shape as well as the height of the entire intensity dome.

Altogether, with Dyn-HTE we managed to devise a method that can reliably compute DSFs for a wide variety of quantum spin models down to $T \simeq J/4$ where many features already resemble their $T = 0$ counterparts. We want to emphasize that there exists no other method that can produce this data for high-dimensional models with frustrated interactions. The flexibility of our open-source code (E) opens the door for further studies of the finite-temperature DSF of a plethora of spin models. Currently we are working on generalizations to XXZ models and models with finite next-nearest neighbor coupling J_2 .

This concludes our summary of results generated in this DFG-funded project. While we had to abandon the diagrammatic resummation by spin-fRG due to a lack of reliable truncation scheme, we explored various other resummation schemes of high order diagrammatic expansions of spin correlators. This finally led us to the Dyn-HTE, that allowed us to study the DSF for spin models which seemed far out of reach at the beginning of this project.

Data handling and availability All publications are available via the open-access preprint server *arXiv.org*. Publications (A) and (B) contain all necessary data to be fully reproducible. For projects (C) and (D), the series expansion coefficients can be accessed via the well documented open source code (E). Here, tutorials and plot scripts for the plots in articles (C) and (D) are available.

Scientific communication measures The results of projects (A) and (B) were presented at the *DPG Frühjahrstagung 2024* in Berlin and the *12th International Conference on the Exact Renormalization Group 2024* in Les Diablerets, Switzerland as well as at the *Munich Conference on Quantum Science and Technology 2024 and 2025* in Sonthofen and Kufstein, respectively. Results of projects (C) and (D) will be presented at *Korrelationstage 2025* and *Workshop Current Trends in Strongly Correlated and Frustrated Systems 2025*, both in Dresden.

3.3 Bibliography

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Peer-reviewed publications

(A) Dipolar ordering transitions in many-body quantum optics: Analytical diagrammatic approach to equilibrium quantum spins.

B. Schneider, R. Burkard, B. Olmos, I. Lesanovsky, B. Sbierski. *Phys. Rev. A* **110**, 063301 (2024). DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevA.110.063301](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.110.063301). **Open Access:** Yes <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.18156>.

(B) Taming Spin Susceptibilities in Frustrated Quantum Magnets: Mean-Field Form and Approximate Nature of the Quantum-to-Classical Correspondence.

B. Schneider, B. Sbierski. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **134**, 176502 (2025). DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevLett.134.176502](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.134.176502). **Open Access:** Yes. Open Access via [PhysRevLett](https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.12776)

4.2 Category B – Other outputs (preprints, datasets, software)

(C) High-temperature series expansion of the dynamic Matsubara spin correlator.

R. Burkard, B. Schneider, B. Sbierski. [arXiv:2505.23699](https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.23699) (2025). **Open Access:** Yes (preprint). Under review at Phys. Rev. B.

(D) Dynamic correlations of frustrated quantum spins from high-temperature expansion.

R. Burkard, B. Schneider, B. Sbierski. [arXiv:2505.14571](https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.14571) (2025). **Open Access:** Yes (preprint). Under review at Phys. Rev. Lett.

(E) Public Dyn-HTE software: Dynamic correlations of quantum spins from high-temperature expansion, contains precomputed graph-evaluations, pre-defined lattices and many examples (<https://github.com/bsbierski/Dyn-HTE>).

4.3 Patents

None.